

INVESTMENT CREDIT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article describes the role of investment in the industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan and issues related to the territorial features of the implementation of activities. In the effective implementation of investment activities in the republic, along with the formation of mechanisms for attracting investment, its improvement, the presentation of promising project proposals to business entities wishing to invest, systemic support for the development and implementation of high-quality projects, scientific interaction with foreign investors. On its basis, proposals and recommendations for mutually beneficial cooperation, the creation of favorable conditions for the activities of investors, and the attraction of investment have been developed.*

Keywords: *industry, investment activity, investment fund, project, entity, mechanism, domestic and foreign investment, investment activity.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that investments are becoming increasingly important in the modernization, technical and technological renewal of the economy, radical change and diversification of its structure, ensuring high, stable and proportional economic growth. According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-459 on December 28, 2022 "On measures to implement the investment program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2023-2025" for 2023-2025, the following were approved:

- Aggregate target indicators of centralized and decentralized investments;
- Target indicators for the development of investments and loans in industries and regions.

The stability of the economy of our republic and its individual regions, social, economic and political development are inextricably linked with investment policy.

Definitely, attracting investments is important for reducing mutual economic differences and discrepancies between the regions of our country. Effective use of these opportunities creates the basis for the rational use of all available resources of the regions and structural improvement of the regional economy. It is known from the experience of foreign countries that foreign investments are one of the main mechanisms for ensuring stable development of the country's economy. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the issue of attracting investments, especially foreign ones, into the economy of our country as an important factor in economic growth.

According to the 26th goal of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" for further improving the investment environment in the country and increasing its attractiveness, 120 billion US dollars were given for investment in the next five years. An important factor in the development of investment activities is also the fact that the task has been set to take measures to attract foreign investment in dollars. The construction industry also plays an important role in achieving this goal. The construction sector is one of the industries that contributes to the stable growth of the national economy of our country. According to statistics, in January-December 2022, a total of 130,767.1 billion dollars were produced in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Construction

work in Uzbekistan has been completed, the growth rate compared to the corresponding period of 2021 was 106.6%. The indicators of construction work by types of economic activity showed that: the direction of construction of buildings and structures (89,379.6 billion soums) accounted for 68.4 percent, and the growth rate in 2021 increased by 104.4% compared to the same period of the previous year; the direction of construction of civil facilities (28,139.0 billion soums) accounted for 21.5% of the share, and the growth rate reached 102.7%. The share of specialized construction work (13,248.5 billion soums) accounts for 10.1% and the growth rate is 138.2%. Construction activity is the result of its own construction work, new construction, the volume of major and current repairs. According to the head of our country Sh. Mirziyoyev, "A country pursuing an active investment policy has achieved stable growth of its economy. That is why investments are the drivers of the economy; it will not be an exaggeration to say that this is the heart of the economy of Uzbekistan". Positive results in the economy make it possible to systematically solve accumulated problems in the social sphere.

It is important to suggest that we must build our work on this basis. In order to attract foreign investment, it is necessary to take measures to fully demonstrate the investment potential of our country, which should be one of the most pressing issues in our daily lives [1], noting that foreign investment is extremely important in the development of the economy shows the importance and relevance of its participation.

An investment environment has been created in our country that meets international requirements. In particular, the adoption of Law LRU-598 "On Investments and Investment Activities" dated December 25, 2019 has a positive impact on the investment potential of Uzbekistan. This law provides for a number of benefits and preferences for state support for investments and investment activities.

Certainly, the government has created all the conditions for investors, widespread attraction of foreign direct investment and high technologies in the economic sector, ensuring the social and economic efficiency of investment projects, creating high-income jobs on this basis and determines the relevance of the chosen topic in the future implementation of such tasks as advanced socio-economic development of regions.

While suggesting the analysis of literature regarding investments, their active attraction, creation of a favorable investment environment requires the study of factors influencing investment activity in the development of the national economy, including direct, foreign investments and enterprises with their participation. There are developments of many domestic and foreign scientists on the role and importance of organizing investments in the development of economic activity in the regions.

For example, according to one of the foreign economists K. Eklund, investments are something left for tomorrow so that in the future there will be more conditions for consumption. Part of it is consumer goods that are not currently used, and the other part is resources aimed at expanding production. [3]

According to E.D. Dolan and D.S. Lindsay, the meaning of investments is "the growth of capital in a developing economic system, an increase in the supply of productive resources that people use". [4] Due to W. Sharpe, investments are parting with a certain amount of money today in order to get more funds in the future. [5]

Additionally, according to L. Gitman, M. Jonk, investments are the placement of capital in such a way that its value is preserved, grows and brings a positive amount of income. [15]

According to K. McConnell, S. Brew, investments are an increase in material reserves, the accumulation of means of production and production costs [15]. According to R. Samuelson, V. Nordhaus, investments are an economic state that means the rejection of today's consumption expenses for the sake of expanding production in the future. In it, funds are directed to tangible or intangible capital.

According to financiers, investments imply the purchase of securities.[15] Also, leading scientists of our republic D. Gozibekov, B.A. Abdukarimov, A.N. Jabriyev, M.K. Pardayev, D. Tojiboyeva, B.A. Abdukarimov, A.N. Jabriev, and others conducted scientific research and expressed their opinion. According to D. Gozibekov, the purpose of investments is to obtain funds from clear and reliable sources, mobilize them in a reasonable way, preserve the value of capital taking into account the level of risks and obtain the planned effect. [15]

According to Pardayev, investments are investments in financial (money) or real capital. It is carried out in the form of cash, credit, securities and is invested in movable and immovable property, intellectual property, rights to benefits and other values, i.e., it is used for all assets of the enterprise.[10] According to D. Tojiboyeva, investments are financial resources intended for future results: expansion or renewal of production, improvement of the quality of products and services, training of qualified specialists, conducting scientific research. [11]

Based on the results of theoretical research of foreign and our domestic scientists, we came to the following conclusion: the scientific basis of investments is the resource and cost approaches, their initial organization requires the use of funds, the social sphere, entrepreneurship to implement investments. profit - tangible and intangible assets and rights to them, including rights to intellectual property included in the objects of scientific and other types of risk-based activities. In our opinion, investments are capital that has not yet been materialized, but is invested in the means of production, in their financial form, they are assets invested in economic activity in order to make a profit.

Research methodology. It is worth mentioning that in the course of our study, we used the methods of statistical processing, analysis, expert assessment, systems approach, comparison and comparative analysis by grouping data on the volume of investments in fixed assets by regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Currently, one of the most important tasks in the field of economic development is to create favorable conditions for attracting foreign investment in the economy of our country, introduce practical mechanisms for their legal protection, and further improve the investment climate.

At present time, most of the construction work carried out in our country is related to the construction of new buildings and structures, 68.6% of the total volume of construction work or 89,695.5 billion rubles. Construction work soums are aimed at creating new production facilities, housing and other social facilities in the economy. The work was performed for the amount of soums, or the share of large construction organizations in new construction was 32.6%-59.1% or 159.6 trillion soums of investments in fixed assets in January-December 2022. 40.9% or 110.3 trillion soums were financed through attracted funds, own funds of enterprises, organizations and residents. In January-December 2022, 15.2 trillion soums were financed through external loans guaranteed by the Republic of Uzbekistan. Soum investments were utilized and amounted to 74.9% compared to 2021. Their share in the total volume decreased by 2.0% and was fixed at 5.6%. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the volume of investments aimed at the development of infrastructure, economic and social spheres, financed from the republican budget, compared to

2021, amounted to 84.4% or 20.9 trillion soums. Also, investments from the fund for the development of water supply and sanitation systems increased by 92.0% - 2.9 trillion soums compared to 2021. Their share in the total investment volume decreased by 0.1 percentage points and amounted to 1.1%.

Table 1. Investments in fixed capital by sources of financing

	billion soums	growth rate, in percent	share of total, in percent
Investments in fixed capital	12 251,9	118,3	100,0
Including			
Centralized investments:	1 005,5	50,8	8,2
Budget funds	724,0	88,0	5,9
Fund for the development of water supply and sewage systems	61,0	88,6	0,5
Foreign loans guaranteed by the Republic of Uzbekistan	220,5	20,3	1,8
Decentralized investments	11 246,4	134,3	91,8
Funds of enterprises (including local budget funds)	3 821,0.	2,1 m	31,2
Funds of the population	585,5	82,6	4,8
Direct and other foreign investments and loans	3 828,3	86,0	31,3
Commercial bank loans and other borrowed funds	3 011,6.	2,1 m	24,5

Statistical calculation of investments in fixed assets is carried out in the amount of the actually acquired volume, regardless of the time of payment, including value added tax, in current prices of the reporting period. The highest indicators and growth rates by sources of financing investments in fixed assets corresponded to the own funds of enterprises and organizations and amounted to 110.6 percent compared to 2021. The investment amounts were mastered, and the share of investments in the total volume of fixed assets amounted to 22.3%. For January-December 2022, investments in fixed assets financed from the own funds of enterprises and organizations - 84.5 trillion. soums or 31.3% of the total volume of investments in fixed assets. The manufacturing industry is the leader in the structure of investments in fixed assets by type of economic activity.

Organization of production of new car models (Onyx, Tracker), expansion of cement production (3rd stage), organization of industrial gas production, organization of a complex for the production of mineral fertilizers, organization of a cotton-textile and agro-cluster accounts for 76.4 trillion soums or 28.3% of the total volume of capital investments from general sources of financing in this type of economic activity as a result of the implementation of large investment projects.

While assessing the innovative potential of regions, the economic growth of the region, as well as the innovative potential of the region, the indicators that determine the state policy in the development of the region and important ways to attract investment to the region were determined. The data used are based on the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For January-June 2023, investments in fixed assets amounted to 12,251.9 billion soums and increased by 118.3% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year.

By summerising it should be suggested that for increasing the investment potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to present promising project proposals for business entities wishing to invest, to systematically ensure the development and implementation of high-quality projects, as well as mutually beneficial cooperation with foreign partners, it is necessary to create favorable conditions for the activities of investors, to develop measures to attract investment. From the figures given, we see that the investment environment in our country is improving year after year, and the population's income is growing. In the context of economic modernization, one of the important tasks of investment policy is to create an economic basis for the correct determination of the direction and distribution of regulation of investment processes, to ensure conditions that ensure the implementation of a developed policy, and this is what contributes to economic growth, which can be achieved along the way.

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